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The Role of Sustainable Industry Clusters in Regional Competitiveness in Times of Crisis

KEYWORDS

regional economy, integration, regional competitiveness, economic cluster

ABSTRACT

Introduction. The urgency stems from the need to increase regional stability, strengthen competitiveness, and improve the efficient utilization of resources amid the economic crisis.

The article analyzes the impact of sustainable industry clusters on regional competitiveness during the economic crisis.

Materials and methods. The study relied on scientific articles from highly ranked international journals and conference proceedings on the impact of clusters on regional sustainability. It also incorporated practical cases of successful cluster initiatives in times of crisis and an analysis of globalization tools that contribute to enhancing regional competitiveness.

Results. The article examines the problem of globalization of economic processes resulting from the activities of large economic entities—regions—in the process of integration into the world economy and international economic relations. The main directions and models of regional competitiveness formation, as well as the regional clusters that underpin economic globalization, are analyzed.

Conclusion. Globalization increases the need for regions to identify and develop their sustainable competitive advantages to mitigate economic instability and crises. Successful development depends on the clear identification of key competitive factors, including the development of industries that foster international competition and integration synergies.

FOR CITATION

Received: Jun 30, 2025
Accepted: Sep 2, 2025
Published: Dec 1, 2025

Koshkarev, M. V., & Satmurzaev, A. A. (2025). The Role of Sustainable Industry Clusters in Regional Competitiveness in Times of Crisis. *Economic Consultant*, (4), 39–54. <https://doi.org/10.46224/ecoc.2025.4.3>

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INTRODUCTION

Significant changes in the structure of the regional economy, price dynamics, production volumes, the ratio of labor productivity to income, and patterns of accumulation and consumption accompany fluctuations in economic phases (increases, decreases). At the same time, the national characteristics of instability depend on the structure and state of economic systems at both national and regional levels, as well as on the degree of their integration into the world economy, their industrial potential, and financial capacity at the time of crisis emergence, among other factors. Regions whose economies are based on only one or two sectors, and whose enterprises within them produce raw materials or intermediate products, are much more vulnerable.

Undoubtedly, the current instability and turbulence are exacerbated by the unpredictable and spontaneous development of globalization, which highlights issues associated with the adaptability and flexibility of regional economic systems. In such circumstances, due to significant differences in monetary and financial capacities, interactions between regions, both within a particular state and at the transnational level, are becoming increasingly asymmetric.

The problems of stabilizing economic systems, regardless of their scale (state or region), cannot be solved using classical theoretical models. As noted by Thomas Hoerber and Alain Anquetil, economic theory, currently in crisis, is not yet able to generate effective solutions to problems stemming from instability and demonstrates some detachment from the empirical laws governing integration and globalization [1].

Effective development of the regional economic system, amid intensifying globalization and integration pressures, implies the need for consistent application of various financial regulation methods and tools, conducting in-depth studies of development conditions, and identifying prerequisites for increasing regional competitiveness during periods of instability and crisis.

According to the author, given the current situation, the concept of glocality is the most appropriate, as it leverages the opportunities and advantages of globalization to increase regions' competitiveness during a crisis. This concept is based on the paradigm of the interrelation of local and global economic interests. In accordance with this concept, the ability of any region to transform its traditional economic resources into global advantages and to create unique, locally rooted competitive values determines its capacity to respond adequately to modern economic challenges of instability [2].

This assumption is supported by leading international institutions and organizations that assess country competitiveness, which include certain national regions of certain states in their ratings. For example, OECD representatives note that support for positive regional dynamics has become a key issue in the economic policy of OECD member countries over the past decade. This is explained by the fact that only 10% of the regions accounted for more than half of all jobs during 1996-2018. This state of affairs allows us to assert that a country's general well-being is determined by a limited number of national regions [3].

In practice, this concept involves developing a model of regional economic policy based not solely on traditional levers managing existing resources but on the full utilization of opportunities provided by the geo-economic environment and the region's geographical location. In other words, a key development mechanism is the management of market opportunities, which involves the inclusion of the region and its economic actors in external production and value chains, thereby expanding the scope of regional management beyond administrative and territorial boundaries. This, in turn, enables the creation of a fundamentally new type of regional economic policy which is focused on securing leading competitive positions and avoiding traditional forms of competition. This policy involves developing the region's unique features, organizing the production of new products, creating new markets, and concentrating logistics flows through its integration into the global system of relations.

The classic model for the formation of the region's competitiveness, including in times of crisis, which fails to leverage the opportunities and advantages of globalization, is as follows (see Fig. 1).

As shown in Fig. 1, the regional competitiveness model comprises two groups of factors: the "inherited" and the "created". The first group is formed at the state level and implemented through state policy; the second is formed at the regional level.

Obviously, in the traditional model, the basis of regional competitiveness is state economic and social policy. With measures such as taxes, depreciation rates, preferences, and wage regulation, the fundamental conditions for effective management are established [4]. State policy, except for specific preferences for depressed territories, creates equal conditions for all regions and can be considered a constant (for a particular period).

Despite the importance of state policy, significant actions must also be taken at the regional level. The merit of the regional community and authorities lies in

the effective utilization of the resources and factors at their disposal, including, for example, the transitive or border placement of the territory and agglomeration effects. The level of the territory's competitiveness depends on the activities of regional authorities and entrepreneurial and public elites. This partly explains the uneven development of regions.

Figure 1 Regional Competitiveness Model

If the region takes advantage of globalization opportunities, its competitiveness model is as follows (see Fig. 2).

The model presented in Fig. 2 differs from the traditional one (see Fig. 1) by including an additional set of factors affecting regional competitiveness. As noted earlier, these factors, related to the global business environment, create both additional opportunities and threats.

Opportunities to strengthen competitiveness include: enhancing investment support for competitive positions through foreign capital, especially foreign direct investment; strengthening technological components ("technological competitiveness"); adopting organizational innovations; implementing international industrial cooperation; and similar measures [5].

Figure 2 Model of Regional Competitiveness Building Using Globalization Opportunities

Globalized regions actively leverage these opportunities, initiating an acceleration mechanism to increase competitiveness. Access to world markets enables them to attract external resources, including financial and non-financial, to strengthen competitive positions, allowing their use in increasingly larger volumes, thereby boosting competitiveness.

At the same time, new threats to regional competitiveness arise, referred to in Figure 2 as “global degradations”. These represent foreign economic threats. Therefore, counteracting global destruction is an essential component of leveraging globalization advantages when selecting and implementing measures to overcome a crisis. The corresponding measures should be included in the policy framework for strengthening regional competitiveness.

The article aims to analyze the impact of sustainable industry clusters on regional competitiveness amid the economic crisis.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

When studying the topic, scientific articles on the impact of clusters on the economic sustainability of regions, published in highly rated international journals (*Journal of the Knowledge Economy, Leadership, Education, Personality: An Interdisciplinary Journal, Review of Regional Research, The Annals of Regional Science, Smart Innovation, Systems and Technologies, Finance, Economics, and Industry for Sustainable Development, Journal of the Knowledge Economy, etc.*), as well as abstracts of international conferences (INTERAGROMASH 2022, Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, ICBE 2023 Springer Proceedings in Business and Economics, etc.) were analyzed.

Practical studies of successful cluster initiatives in a crisis were also utilized, in particular, specific globalization tools that enhance regional competitiveness during crises.

SOURCE OVERVIEW

The cluster approach contributes to regional competitiveness by fostering enterprise cooperation, innovation, cost reduction, and efficiency, as well as by stimulating regional specialization and attracting investment.

D. Celetti et al. argue that without careful consideration, the cluster approach risks being superficial, failing to address core problems, and being quickly supplanted by other “fashionable” concepts, without significantly impacting the innovative development of industrial regions. Scientists have identified historical, structural, and evolutionary features of cluster development, which enable the creation of practical tools for implementing cluster policy in a region [6].

B. A. Bittencourt et al. note that the question of how geographical clusters affect companies' innovative activities remains unresolved in the literature. Scientists have identified elements of clusters that affect companies' innovative activities: context, collective strategy, public policy, commercialization, proactivity, external relations, cooperation, assimilation, transformation, and application of knowledge, management, infrastructure, as well as financial and human resources [7].

P. Ganske and C. C. Carbon write that the creation of clusters promotes the idea that a network of companies combining cooperative and competitive practices generates competitive advantages for a given territory. The authors found that prevailing cluster policies often do not lead to consistently

successful clusters; sustainable cluster development requires a shared vision among participants, fostering a sense of belonging, social identity, and the internalization of values and attitudes [8].

N. Grashof shows that the ability of family businesses to innovate depends on the regional context. Within regional clusters, family businesses can leverage localization externalities, resulting in more radical innovations than firms outside clusters [9].

The regional specificity of the cluster approach lies in considering local features and resources, the flexibility to adapt to regional conditions and infrastructure, and the need to form clusters aligned with specific industries and the region's competitive advantages.

M. G. Allabyan notes that the cluster mechanism for implementing industrial policy has demonstrated high efficiency over the past two decades, particularly at the regional level. The authors analyze the prerequisites for the formation of a territorial timber industry cluster in the Khanty-Mansiysk Autonomous Okrug – Ugra. They further consider the developed tools of regional industrial policy for the creation and development of a sectoral timber cluster and conclude that positive economic effects are anticipated [10].

O. V. Cherkashina et al. examine the role of clusters in ensuring regional sustainable development and identify distinctive features as forms of cooperation within regional production frameworks. The authors describe cluster enterprises in the Kaliningrad region and propose new development directions [11].

I. Kedrova et al. consider the prerequisites and features of forming an excursion cluster for industrial tourism, as this type of territorial development is increasingly in demand in Rostov Region of the Russian Federation. Scientists note increased tourist attention compared to previous seasons, with city-forming enterprises and unique industrial facilities such as Rostselmash and Lemax, Bio-Khutor Petrovsky, and the specially protected Don Valley winery playing a pivotal role [12].

S. G. Azizova considers the role of clusters in the consumer market and their impact on regional economic development, examining the Sughd region of Tajikistan. Scientists determined that introducing the concept of clustering supports the formation of sustainable economic structures and increases the competitiveness of local enterprises. In the consumer market, clusters facilitate the development of innovative products and services, improve quality, and reduce costs through resource sharing and lessons learned [13].

C. Coman & V. Cojanu found that more than half of Romanian counties have substantial potential for developing clusters in primary industries—agriculture, forestry, fishing, mining, and quarrying. The researchers concluded that Romania requires significant investment in knowledge and innovation, intelligent systems along the value chain, and the promotion of national and international cooperation [14].

J. L. Christensen & D. Störning develop the concept of “cluster entrepreneurs” as key actors in cluster formation, illustrating this with a Danish biomedical technology cluster initiative [15].

C. R. China et al. describe the Innovative Systems and Cluster Development Program implemented in Tanzania, a successful collaboration among cluster companies, universities, local governments, and research institutes. Implementation of collaborative guidelines has fostered innovation, knowledge sharing, internships, and long-term partnerships through Memoranda of Understanding [16].

A. Andhale & S. Rath write that industrial locations in India demonstrate sustained geographic clustering, resulting in significant regional imbalances in formal employment. Scientists focus on the dispersion of enterprises outside dominant clusters into low-industrialization areas [17].

D. Kim et al. quantify the growth and decline of industrial clusters by validating actual models. The authors analyzed data from 1,375 industrial clusters in South Korea over 20 years [18].

F. Suárez et al. present strategies to assess technological innovation among Ecuadorian textile companies post-pandemic. Clustering allows identification of common goals and projects, simplifies financing, develops technological innovation strategies to increase competitiveness and productivity, and achieves the necessary level of internationalization. They also suggest targeted subsector clustering and innovation-capital integration for competitiveness [19].

Numerous methods for forming clusters exist, including analytical, institutional, strategic, and innovative. Models can be centralized, decentralized, or hybrid, focused on developing existing or creating new clusters.

C. P. Chain & L. G. de Castro Junior use geostatistical techniques to map potential industrial clusters, measuring the proximity between firms, identifying regions with high industrial concentration, and assessing the concentration index at the firm level [20].

The cluster type models highlighted by D. Napolskikh consider spatial concentration of production, institutional environment, innovative business networks, and digital

infrastructure. Scientists proposed an innovative hypercluster model, representing the development of multi-cluster structures in the digital economy [21].

Y. Tan et al. introduced a method using extensive enterprise data and semantic similarity to identify industrial clusters, enabling rapid identification and quantitative assessment of industry connections and spatial coordination at the enterprise level [22].

G. Christopoulos & R. Wintjes presented an indicator to identify innovative clusters beyond traditional industry taxonomies, integrating knowledge creation and use into regional economic systems. Such clusters facilitate feedback mechanisms between knowledge demand and supply and include both high-tech industries and those with centuries-old geographically concentrated production specializations [23].

G. Jain et al. note that SME clusters often face conflicts and deadlocks impeding operational dynamics. The authors explore blockchain technology for collaborative SME cluster management using community self-governance principles [24].

When forming clusters, environmental sustainability must be considered, minimizing negative impacts, adopting eco-friendly technologies, preserving biodiversity, and ensuring rational natural resource use.

V. Y. Akhmetov et al. analyzed agro-industrial cluster development. They argue that the multiplier effect allows agribusiness clustering to contribute to rural development, improve quality of life, organize new enterprises, diversify rural economies, create jobs, and enhance transport, engineering, and social infrastructure [25].

Y. Liu et al. examine industrial clusters' impact on corporate carbon emissions in China (2008-2020). They found that stronger industrial clusters correlate with lower carbon intensity, and heterogeneity across clusters significantly affects carbon reduction performance [26].

Rui Wang writes that clusters and hubs have become key topics in carbon capture, utilization, and storage (CCUS). By sharing costs, risks, benefits, and results, clusters and hubs facilitate large-scale CCUS application [27].

Thus, studies show that without deep understanding, the cluster approach may be superficial and ineffective for regional innovation. Historical, structural, and evolutionary features must be considered to form practical development tools.

Currently, methods to map and analyze industrial clusters include geostatistics, spatial concentration models, innovative networks, and digital technologies. New approaches enable rapid cluster identification using big data and semantic analysis, as well as indicators for innovative and multi-vector clusters.

Figure 4 Cluster Imaging in Europe by K-Means [29]

Over the past few years, more than 1,850 companies have concentrated in Austria's 90 largest business parks and industrial zones, with numbers continuing to grow [30].

In the cross-border industrial park Heiligenkreuz-Sentgotthard (Austria-Hungary), over 30 enterprises in construction, food, engineering, logistics, consulting, and transport operate on 30 hectares [31].

Access Industrial Park Gmünd-České Velenice (Austria-Czech Republic) is Europe's first cross-border business park with an integrated incubator and service center, hosting more than 40 high-tech firms across 83 hectares (33 Austrian, 50 Czech) [32].

2. *Enhancing free trade zone potential.* Overcoming regional economic turbulence requires active engagement with free trade zones. Key steps include:

- intensifying and establishing temporary “beacons” for practical adaptation of technical regulations and documents;
- Harmonizing national sanitary and phytosanitary measures with international standards and ensuring their implementation at all levels of the system hierarchy of regional economic management;
- Developing support systems for regional producers to certify products for competitive exports;
- Facilitating contacts with potential importers and creating information databases.

3. *Attracting to the region and supporting integrated economic entities;* transnational corporations (TNCs), multinational corporations (MNCs), alliances,

and other networked groups of enterprises. Integrated business structures have undeniable advantages over individual enterprises due to the great potential to attract external financing, the vast possibilities for combining resources, the use of significant amounts of information, etc. American researchers Mark J. Melitz, M. Obstfeld, and P. Krugman note a scale effect in the geographical concentration of business entities, highlighting external and internal economies of scale. The former result from the concentration of enterprises (even small ones) in a particular region, where their interaction and cooperation can reduce average costs. The latter arise directly at the level of the business entity itself – the company; the larger it is, the lower its average costs. These conditions establish a competitive advantage for the region. “In the context of globalization, it is not decentralized enterprises that compete in the global economy, but industrial clusters – groups of enterprises organized as networks” [33].

4. Developing and improving the foreign economic activity logistics of the region.

In a crisis, when traditional trade and economic ties are suspended or disrupted, the flows of raw materials, resources, and other goods slow down or even freeze. New logistics routes for domestic goods transportation and for the import of necessary raw materials hold significant potential for efficiency gains.

In this context, special emphasis should be placed on the feasibility of establishing trade and logistics centers to leverage the region's economic and geographical potential effectively. The functioning features of such centers are as follows:

- the infrastructure that arises directly in and around the distribution center (gas stations, cafes, hostels, hotels, office service centers, banks, currency exchange offices) boosts employment and improves the living standard of the local population;
- high standards in presenting a wide range of goods and in sales conditions create a competitive advantage for trade and logistics centers compared to small trading enterprises and sellers of smuggled products;
- exhibition areas for professional presentation of the region's products, along with conditions for executing large contracts, stimulate entrepreneurial and investment initiatives.

5. Expanding the practices of joint (with international partners) implementation of projects for the creation of industrial territorial-sectoral production systems, thereby ensuring a synergistic effect in the form of strengthened innovation competitiveness, increased efficiency of local production, and a greater number of innovatively

active business entities. The elements of such systems are large, medium, and small enterprises, universities, and research institutions. Large enterprises oversee efficiency, strategic planning, and production of standard mass products, semi-finished products, and, especially, complex equipment. The primary goal of medium- and small-sized enterprises, with their flexibility and mobility, is to produce innovative goods that require constant adaptation to a rapidly changing cross-border market. Universities serve as a source of qualified labor; thanks to them, scientific knowledge is transformed into practical qualifications. Research institutions are tasked with conducting ongoing innovation processes and ensuring the reproduction of technological innovations.

6. *Use of a wide range of cross-border financing instruments, such as technical assistance, budget support, macro-financial assistance, and project-specific funding.* Globalization and the integration of financial systems offer significant opportunities for regions to attract financial resources from international structural funds, such as the EU, during crises. Such loans are mainly directed to joint projects between foreign donors and local communities, a common mechanism for addressing problems that contributes to increasing the regions' competitiveness. Notably, such financing is targeted and typically requires the contribution of local funds amounting to 10% or more. Therefore, these instruments of cross-border cooperation should be considered a mechanism that, by accumulating a relatively small share of local funds, helps attract external financial resources and has a substantial socio-economic impact in the region.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Thus, an analysis of a wide range of theoretical and analytical sources on the factors that strengthen a region's competitiveness in times of crisis through globalization's advantages and opportunities leads to the following conclusions.

Globalization necessitates that regions identify and develop their sustainable competitive advantages as a criterion for resilience amid economic instability and increasingly frequent crises. Transformation of regions into strategic players in global markets requires clearly identified determinants of competitiveness, enabling them to overcome economic turbulence.

Undoubtedly, regions facing economic challenges should pay attention not only to the interregional cooperation component but also to the development of industries and economic sectors, considering their international competitiveness

and suitability for integration synergies. The successful use of global advantages relies on both the individual industries competitiveness at the regional level, which helps implement modern forms of cooperation (clusters or technoparks), and on economic structures complementarity across regions worldwide.

In the course of the research, the author formalized a model of traditional regional competitiveness, based on two groups of factors: those formed at the state level and implemented through state policy, and those formed directly within the region. Additionally, a model of competitiveness for a globalizing region is presented, building upon traditional factors and supplemented by capabilities generated by the global business environment.

The author highlighted the following key determinants of global transformations that regional authorities, entrepreneurs, and business structures can use to support and stimulate economic recovery from crises:

1. Implementation of various territorial cooperation forms;
2. Maximizing the potential of free trade zones;
3. Attracting and supporting integrated economic entities in the region;
4. Developing and improving logistics infrastructure for foreign economic activity;
5. Expanding joint projects with international partners to establish industrial territorial-sectoral production systems.
6. Utilizing cross-border financing instruments.
7. Integrating regional industries and enterprises into global value chains.

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The authors have declared that no competing interests exist

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Editor: Daniela Antonescu. Romanian Academy (Romania)